

The effect of ionic surfactants on the behavior of phenols on bismuth tungstate thin layers

Shail Kulshrestha*, S. K. Dabral, K. P. S. Muktawat and J. C. Pant

Department of Chemistry, Government. P. G. College, Rishikesh-249 201, India

E-mail : gpgcri@sancharnet.in Fax : 91-0135-430495

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The effect of surfactants on the behavior of phenolics on bismuth tungstate thin layers has been studied by employing various developing solvents of different nature. HR_f values are compared with those obtained on unimpregnated silica gel layers. It is observed that the utilization of micellar mobile phases, which improves the selectivity and compactness of the spots, offers significant advantage over traditional developing systems. A number of binary and ternary separations of phenols are reported.

A number of chromogenic reagents¹ have been reported for the detection of phenolic compounds on thin layer plates. Because of rapidity, simplicity, low cost and excellent resolving power, silica gel thin layer chromatography has been extensively used for identification and separation of organic compounds². Behavior of phenols on unimpregnated thin layers have been reported by various workers³. But little effort has been made to utilize inorganic ion-exchangers which show high separation potentialities as absorbents⁴ for thin layer chromatography of phenols.

The effects of micellar mobile phase on chromatographic behavior of wide variety of organic compounds have been described⁵. In continuation of our interest in this field, the effect of ionic surfactants on the chromatographic behavior of phenols was studied on bismuth tungstate thin layers by adding sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) of different concentration in mobile phase systems. For comparison purpose the movement of phenolics was observed on unimpregnated silica gel thin layers under identical conditions. Some of the important separations achieved are reported.

Results and Discussion

The HR_f values of phenolic compounds in various developing systems are presented in Table 1. The phenolic spots in most of the developing systems are found compact and well defined on bismuth tungstate thin layers in comparison to plain silica gel thin layer plates in which the spots show some trailing⁶. It has been observed that the movement of the phenols in most of the cases is lower than that observed on unimpregnated thin layers. This shows that the bismuth tungstate thin layers serve as a good absorbent for phenols and its immobilization on the thin layer retards

the movement of various phenols to different extent⁷.

On the unimpregnated silica gel thin layers, however, there is no such retardation force and hence a high HR_f values are observed than on bismuth tungstate thin layers. Besides absorptivity, HR_f value also depends on the kind of mobile phase system used. The results show that there is an increase in the HR_f values of phenols with increase in concentration of ammonium hydroxide. This behavior can be attributed to the high solubility of phenols in higher concentration of ammonium hydroxide. For the similar reason HR_f value of phenol increases when concentration of sodium nitrate solution increases. Among other developing systems studied, formic acid based systems are also important and can be employed for selective separation of phenolic compounds.

In thin layer plates impregnated with inorganic ion-exchangers partition, adsorption as well as ion-exchange mechanism are operative, and selectively of the exchanger is also one of the significant advantage. By introducing ionic surfactants in mobile phase, the electrostatic interaction between charged solutes and ionic micelles can be achieved which not only modify the partition coefficient between micelles and aqueous phase (P_{MW}) but also modify the interactions with stationary phase because the increase in polarity of the solute reduces the partition coefficient between the stationary phase and aqueous phase (P_{SW})⁸.

It is also observed that movement of phenols are not appreciably affected by the addition of surfactants to the mobile phase solvents, however, the compactness of the spots is improved. But increasing the concentration of SDS in the mobile phase tended to decrease the movement of the phenols. This behavior is to be expected since increasing

Table 1. HR_f values of some phenols on bismuth tungstate thin layers in various mobile phases(S₁-S₁₀)*

Phenol**	S ₁				S ₂				S ₃				S ₄				S ₅			
	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
Phenols	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	85	81	77	81	
Catechol	10	12	10	08	12	08	06	04	58	53	52	48	61	56	54	52	14	12	12	12
Resorcinol	68	64	63	63	66	66	57	63	39	38	38	34	48	46	46	43	67	70	66	70
Quinol	49	49	46	47	50	48	44	45	29	26	26	22	33	31	30	30	74	73	63	68
<i>o</i> -Cresol	14	10	10	07	10	10	10	08	10	08	08	06	01	08	08	04	90	88	88	86
<i>m</i> -Cresol	10	08	06	06	06	06	04	04	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	84	83	83	82
<i>p</i> -Cresol	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	88	86	87	86
α -Naphthol	36	35	31	32	34	25	18	18	34	34	31	29	42	39	38	38	71	70	72	72
β -Naphthol	29	28	28	24	26	25	25	20	24	20	17	17	38	38	34	31	74	73	72	72
Pyrogallol	12	10	10	06	08	06	04	04	26	24	22	19	34	30	29	29	33	32	28	31
Phloroglucinol	16	10	08	07	06	05	03	03	41	37	36	36	22	21	18	17	29	27	22	20
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	71	68	69	67	74	65	63	63	05	02	04	04	09	09	06	04	68	68	67	66
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	64	61	59	54	67	60	58	54	38	37	32	31	46	46	41	39	61	58	58	51
2,4-DNP	39	35	34	34	35	33	33	30	42	39	37	34	47	44	41	42	18	15	15	14
2,4,6-TNP	58	56	57	52	59	55	54	54	62	61	59	58	67	61	59	57	40	38	38	39
<i>o</i> -HBA	28	24	21	21	25	23	20	19	60	54	53	53	66	63	60	59	22	24	21	20
<i>p</i> -HBA	29	30	28	30	27	20	25	26	46	40	42	38	48	49	46	42	74	72	76	73
<i>p</i> -Aminophenol	48	46	51	48	50	51	61	60	21	18	18	17	28	26	25	24	78	78	77	77
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	42	41	41	38	46	46	42	41	50	46	43	41	60	61	60	56	75	72	68	68
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	38	34	30	32	40	42	37	36	00	00	00	00	10	12	08	06	45	43	38	38
Phenols	S ₆				S ₇				S ₈				S ₉				S ₁₀			
	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
Phenols	88	90	87	88	54	52	50	46	77	72	68	62	92	93	89	89	95	94	88	86
Catechol	28	27	25	24	60	60	54	53	68	63	62	58	91	89	83	85	85	83	80	82
Resorcinol	78	75	73	71	70	70	64	59	78	76	72	69	86	84	83	84	87	85	82	78
Quinol	76	74	68	67	84	78	70	68	88	82	76	70	91	90	86	89	90	86	89	85
<i>o</i> -Cresol	94	94	92	92	70	62	60	59	81	76	67	66	95	95	93	92	90	95	94	97
<i>m</i> -Cresol	88	89	87	88	14	10	08	08	53	47	47	38	94	95	93	92	95	96	95	97
<i>p</i> -Cresol	92	90	86	86	32	30	24	18	62	58	51	49	93	90	91	90	91	94	95	96
<i>a</i> -Naphthol	88	89	88	87	79	76	70	68	70	70	62	59	59	62	61	60	94	91	93	93
<i>b</i> -Naphthol	92	91	88	87	50	48	42	40	64	59	54	48	90	94	82	90	95	94	93	93
Pyrogallol	22	20	20	18	70	67	67	59	76	68	61	59	68	67	65	66	68	68	64	61
Phloroglucinol	17	14	14	13	64	61	57	54	67	62	60	52	59	58	52	50	84	64	60	60
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	73	65	65	64	78	70	64	52	56	49	47	47	91	91	93	92	90	96	-	95
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	68	61	61	58	52	47	45	42	66	58	56	53	79	73	71	71	86	80	81	80
2,4-DNP	29	26	24	23	90	82	73	65	84	82	80	79	90	92	89	90	95	87	84	80
2,4,6-TNP	34	32	29	27	85	78	77	68	74	69	65	60	74	78	78	76	68	68	69	70
<i>o</i> -HBA	29	32	28	26	75	71	70	62	78	70	69	66	82	82	80	78	90	90	93	89
<i>p</i> -HBA	58	56	54	-	79	68	61	60	84	79	78	72	79	82	80	81	80	76	76	73
<i>p</i> -Aminophenol	74	69	68	68	93	90	89	88	82	78	78	71	92	90	90	88	90	90	88	86
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	68	62	60	58	46	46	51	60	74	71	68	66	86	84	83	81	87	84	80	80
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	34	36	33	30	79	78	76	69	72	74	70	70	72	69	69	65	74	72	71	70

*Explanation for S₁ to S₁₀ given in the text; A = without surfactant, B = 4 m ML⁻¹ SDS, C = 8 m ML⁻¹ SDS, D = 12 ml ML⁻¹ SDS. ** DNP = Dinitrophenol, TNP = trinitrophenol, HBA = hydrobenzoic acid.

Separation of (HR _f)	From (HR _p)	Developing system
Phenol (00)	2,4-Dinitrophenol (33), chlorophenol (36), quinol (44), resorcinol (57), <i>m</i> -nitrophenol (58), <i>p</i> -aminophenol (60) and <i>o</i> -nitrophenol (63)	S ₂ C
<i>o</i> -Cresol (08)	Quinol (45), <i>o</i> -nitrophenol (63) and resorcinol (63)	S ₂ D
Catechol (12)	Pyrogallol (28), 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (38), <i>o</i> -nitrophenol (62), quinol (63), resorcinol (66), phenol (79) and <i>m</i> -cresol (83)	S ₅ C
2,4-Dinitrophenol (15)	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol (64)	S ₅ C
Catechol (12)	Quinol (68) and resorcinol (70)	S ₅ D
2,4-Dinitrophenol (15)	2,4,6-Trinitrophenol (34), <i>o</i> -chlorophenol (38), <i>m</i> -nitrophenol (51), <i>o</i> -nitrophenol (66) and phenol (81)	S ₅ D
Pyrogallol (21)	2,4,6-Trinitrophenol (34), <i>o</i> -nitrophenol (73), <i>p</i> -aminophenol (73), quinol (75) and resorcinol (78)	S ₆ A
Quinol (68)	α -Naphthol (88) and resorcinol (78)	S ₆ C

Fig. 1. Chromatogram showing compactness of the spots : (A) with SDS in mobile phase and (B) without SDS in mobile phase; (a) 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, (b) *o*-nitrophenol

the surfactant concentration increases the number of micelles in the mobile phase⁹. Further, the observations indicated that the presence of surfactants in the mixed developing systems significantly increases the sharpness and compactness of the spots, resulting in faster and cleaner separations. Thus the use of micellar developing system which increases the resolution of components was found to offer a significant advantage over traditional mobile phase systems¹⁰.

In view of compactness of the spots and the separation possibilities, bismuth tungstate impregnated silica gel layers were found suitable for the analysis of phenolic compounds. As a result, selective separations of some phenols have been

Table 3. Binary separation of phenols on bismuth tungstate thin layers*

Separation of (HR _f)	From (HR _p)	Developing system
Phenol (00)	Pyrogallol (29) : catechol (52)	S ₄ D
<i>o</i> -Cresol (06)	α -Naphthol (30) : 2,4,6-TNP (59)	S ₃ C
Catechol (11)	Pyrogallol (32) : phenol (81)	S ₅ B
2,4-DNP (14)	2,4,6-TNP (39) : <i>o</i> -nitrophenol (66)	S ₅ D
2,4-DNP (14)	2,4,6-TNP (39) : <i>p</i> -aminophenol (77)	S ₅ D
Catechol (24)	<i>o</i> -Aminophenol (57) : phenol (88)	S ₆ D
Pyrogallol (18)	<i>o</i> -Aminophenol (57) : <i>o</i> -cresol (88)	S ₆ D
<i>m</i> -Cresol (08)	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol (45) : <i>p</i> -aminophenol (89)	S ₇ C
<i>p</i> -Cresol (18)	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol (52) : 2,4-DNP (84)	S ₇ A

*DNP = Dinitrophenol, TNP = trinitrophenol.

achieved and reported in Tables 2 and 3.

Experimental

A Stahl type thin layer chromatographic applicator was used to prepare thin layers on glass plates (5 × 20 cm). Sodium dodecyl sulfate (B.D.H.) was purified¹¹. Phenols and other chemicals and solvents were of A.R. grade.

For the visualization of phenolic spots the following locating agents were used : 0.6% (w/v) of aq. chromic acid solution, 2% solution of ferric chloride in HCl, 5% alkaline chloramine-T solution, 2% ferric nitrate solution, 0.25% solution of ammonium vanadate in perchloric acid.

After purification phenols were kept in small dark bottles to prevent their photo chemical oxidation. A 0.2% solution of phenols made either in acetone or ethanol, was used.

Preparation of ion-exchange material and thin layer plates : Bismuth tungstate, used as absorbent, was prepared as follows. A mixture of 0.1 M sodium bismuthate and

0.1 M sodium tungstate solution in ratio of 1 : 1 (v/v), was refluxed for 24 h at 100° and the resulting solid was washed with demineralized water and dried in incubator at 40°. The material was converted into H⁺-form by treating with 2.0 M nitric acid. Finally, it was washed with demineralized water and dried at 40°. The thin layer plates (0.5 mm thickness) were prepared by spreading a slurry of silica gel (50 g) and bismuth tungstate (25 g) in distilled water (100 ml) and activated for 24 h at 60 ± 1°.

Mobile phase systems : Following mobile phase systems were used to observe the behavior of phenolics with or without 4 m ML⁻¹, 8 m ML⁻¹ and 12 m ML⁻¹ sodium dodecyl sulfate, 0.01 M aqueous sodium nitrate (S₁), 0.1 M aqueous sodium nitrate (S₂), 0.01 M ammonium hydroxide (S₃), 0.1 M ammonium hydroxide (S₄), ethanol : water (1 : 1) (S₅), *n*-butanol : water (1 : 1) (S₆), 0.1 M formic acid (S₇), *n*-butanol : formic acid (1 : 1) (S₈), *n*-butanol : formic acid : water (3 : 1 : 1) (S₉) and *n*-butanol : formic acid : water (2 : 1 : 1) (S₁₀).

Procedure : Solutions of phenols were spotted on the activated thin layer plates and dried in air. For binary and ternary separations the previous spots were dried completely before another application to the same spot was made. Then the plates were subjected to development by allowing the developing system to ascend 16 cm in each case. The plate was first dried in air and then sprayed with suitable chromogenic reagents for locating the phenolic spots. The spots were marked immediately and the R_f values were calculated as usual.

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